

Docking Industrial Robot With Mixed Reality

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Abstract—Substantial advancement in productivity, safety, and time efficiency has been achieved by industrial robots across a wide array of industries. However, the considerable dimensions and weight of certain robots can present significant difficulties for workers when it comes to maneuvering them, particularly in cases of multitasking and within a confined workspace. This article presents a three-dimensional holographic representation of an industrial robot model, which introduced a remedy for lowering labor expenses, saving time, and averting the improper positioning of heavy machinery in the workspace. It achieves this by employing mixed reality to dock and guide the robot's movements. In particular, the 3D model gave a solution for simulating the real industrial arm moving and docking in the real environment, with the ability to recognize the obstacles thanks to the spatial awareness feature. This solution provided a 3D model in real dimension for a real robot and, we evaluated the efficacy of the system to reconstruct the barriers in reality that are constraints to the robot's movements and its usability in the managing of the robot virtual replica. It is noticeable that this application can be used in both industrial and medical aspects as well.

Index Terms—Augmented reality, AR, HMD, HoloLens, optical see-through

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, significant technological progress has occurred in various domains, including the refinement of robot design, enhancement of control systems, and the evolution of sensor technology. These advancements have collectively facilitated the safe integration of industrial robots into final assembly lines [1] [2]. Nonetheless, issues related to the device's size and the time needed to set up the system for different positions in the workspace, such as time-consuming processes and safety concerns for the workers. These challenges may prove difficult to rectify. Recently, some researchers have lightened on those challenges and provided some solutions for the mobility of industrial robots. Cogurcu et al. (2022) provided a solution to visualize a robotic arm using HoloLens 2 (HL2). The hologram was fixed in its position and was able to detect the safe zone of the users in the workspace. To do this, they used employed scenarios involving Speed and Separation Monitoring (SSM) and integrated the Augmented Reality (AR) system with the SSM calculations. They showed the robot arm wrapped with a 3D cylinder or cube representing the safe zone [3]. Another study by Hoang et al. (2021) employed augmented reality using HoloLens to develop a robot model incorporating two types of Virtual Barriers for

safety: a Virtual Person Barrier that envelops and tracks the user to prevent collisions with the robot, and Virtual Obstacle Barriers that users can create to protect specific areas from robot entry. The barrier is positioned at the HoloLens headset's location and is monitored using the AR headset's internal sensors. It safeguards the user by moving with the user's headset as they navigate the workspace. To prevent the user from getting distracted during their tasks, the person barrier is represented with spherical markers that have low opacity, outlining the barrier [4]. Other examples of docking surgical robots, van der Schans et al. (2020) conducted a six-week training program for professional nurses and surgeons, covering draping to robot docking, reducing the time required to 5 minutes for draping and 7 minutes for docking [5]. In contrast, Iranmanesh et al. (2010) had a team of nurses trained in robot operation to handle the setup and docking, with the assistant surgeon guiding a scrub nurse in positioning the robot at the patient's side [6].

As far as we know, the process of initially connecting and operating the robot in various workspaces of different sizes still relies entirely on manual methods, heavily dependent on the user's skill and spatial awareness. In our initial study, we propose a digital solution to streamline the manipulation and docking of an industrial robot within the space. This involves introducing a virtual representation of the robot into the real environment, eliminating the need to physically relocate the device between rooms or positions.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Unity 3D environment

The first step involved configuring the Unity3D environment to incorporate Mixed Reality (MR) tools. This was accomplished by importing several packages, including the MR Toolkit Foundation, Standard Assets for scene construction, and the MR OpenXR Plugin, which aided in debugging the HL2 model. The HoloLens 2, a Microsoft-designed and produced head-mounted display (HMD), offers an immersive experience, enabling users to engage with the environment using holograms and activating their senses in the process [7]. The HoloLens 2 visualized the 3D hologram of the industrial robot in real demotions to help the user dock it in the required position considering the obstacles. We integrated the 3D model of the robot with some features provided by Unity 3D to provide a realistic experience of the robot's mobility. For

example, to secure the model to the floor, we implemented the gravity option by incorporating the *Rigidbody* component. For configuring, relocating, and securely docking the model in the designated space, we activated both the *ObjectManipulator* and *NearInteractionGrabbable* components. To ensure the device doesn't collide with nearby obstacles, we enabled spatial awareness within the scene, making the 3D model aware of all mesh lines generated by other objects in the environment, including walls, ceilings, doors, and medical equipment typically found in operating rooms.

B. Deploying the project into HoloLens 2

Our design was implemented on the HoloLens 2 to visualize and interact with the robot within a real-world setting. The tool we developed allows users to view a 3D model of the robot, enabling them to position and manipulate it in all directions on the floor, except for movement along the axis perpendicular to the floor (the y-axis in Unity 3D). Users can grasp the hologram using two fingers (thumb and forefinger) and move it, except when obstacles are obstructing its path in the environment. These obstacles prevent the hologram from crossing them because the HoloLens 2 utilizes spatial mapping to generate a grid mesh that defines the boundaries of the environment. The experiment commenced when users initiated the application on the HoloLens 2, and their initial observation was the creation of a grid mesh covering the environment through the HoloLens 2.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) *Results of the visualization accuracy:* The following image shows the robots after initializing the HoloLens 2 session and docking the robot on the ground because of the gravity function that was integrated before. The hologram shows the Robot in real size to help the user dock it in its correct position as shown in Fig.1. Test session as been performed in the demo area of a robotic company (www.roboticom.it). The spatial

Fig. 1. Virtual cube with a side of 50 cm to verify the real scale projection by the application.

awareness mesh shows in the scene when the user enables it. This feature helps to recognize the barriers in the environment

that restrict the movement or may not allow the robot to dock in the desired position.

IV. CONCLUSION

To enhance industrial procedures and address the challenges related to relocating robotic instruments, we present a solution in the form of a 3D hologram model created using HoloLens 2. This highly accurate virtual representation of the robot allows users to manipulate its position within the current room, accounting for physical obstacles that mimic real-world barriers in the simulation. It's worth noting that the system cannot currently replicate glass panels, and further validation through real-world tests in industrial settings during regular working days is essential. From our perspective, the arrangement of the workspace can be rapidly and effectively planned thanks to the intuitive nature of MR visualization, which offers immediate spatial understanding and awareness of the work environment. This enables assessing whether there is sufficient space for robots, machinery, and human personnel, thereby preventing errors, saving time, and highlighting potential challenges that workers may encounter when transitioning the 3D model into reality.

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